

Reactive Methylene Compounds. Part V*. Condensations with Benzenediazonium Salts

H. G. Garg**

Behaviour of several benzenediazonium chlorides with different benzoylacetones has been studied. The characteristics of the derivatives formed are described.

The earlier communication on the coupling of aromatic diazonium salts with reactive methylene compounds (Garg and Joshi, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 626) was prompted by the desire to determine the structure of the stable form.

The present investigation includes the preparations of some so-called benzeneazo derivatives of benzoylacetones. These derivatives have been synthesised by reacting a few benzenediazonium chlorides with 4-substituted benzoylacetones, namely, 4-chloro-(I: X = Cl), 4-bromo-(I: X = Br), 4-methyl-(I: X = Me) and 4-methoxy-(I: X = OMe) benzoylacetones.

[X = Cl, Br, Me or OMe; R = phenyl or substituted phenyl]

The rate of coupling of various benzoylacetones with a particular benzenediazonium chloride has been found different. The rate of reaction increases when chloro and bromo groups are present in the *para* position in the phenyl group; other group, such as, Me or OMe, decreases the rate of reaction.

All these compounds are highly coloured, crystalline solids, develop red colour with H_2SO_4 (conc.), and are precipitated as such on dilution. These are soluble in ethanol, acetic acid, benzene, etc.

EXPERIMENTAL †

4-Bromo-(Hanus *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1929, 1, 392), 4-chloro-(Hauser *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4023), 4-methyl-(Basu, this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 119), and 4-methoxy-(Horeau and Jacques, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1948, 53) benzoylacetones were prepared from the corresponding acetophenones by condensation with ethyl acetate with the aid of sodium in dry ether.

Benzeneazo-4-chlorobenzoylacetone.—Aniline (0.05M) was diazotised in the usual manner and the filtered diazonium chloride solution was run into a cooled, stirred mixture of crystalline sodium acetate (50 g.) and 4-chlorobenzoylacetone (0.05M) in water (25 c.c.) and ethanol (25 c.c.). Benzeneazo-4-chlorobenzoylacetone began to separate immediately. It was collected after 8 hours and recrystallised from acetic acid. Different derivatives are described in Table I.

Benzeneazo-4-bromobenzoylacetones (Table I), benzeneazo-4-methylbenzoylacetones (Table II), and benzeneazo-4-methoxybenzoylacetones (Table II) were similarly prepared.

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** Present address : Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

† Melting points are uncorrected.

